

Youth Goals

Research Centre

JEAN MONNET MODULE

Report

Academic Programme in EUROPEAN YOUTH POLICIES AND YOUTH GOALS

Salamanca
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OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRAMME

The Academic Programme in European Youth Policies and Youth Goals is part of the Jean Monnet module funded by the European Union in the framework of the Erasmus+ programme. The main objective of this module is to promote excellence in teaching and critical analysis of European public policies aimed at youth, contributing to the strengthening of a young citizenship that is more informed, active and committed to the democratic values of the Union.

The Programme has been designed to address a diverse audience, including university students, young researchers, youth leaders, civil society representatives and practitioners from different backgrounds, both at national and international level. Through specialised and interdisciplinary training, it aims to foster knowledge on Youth Goals as a result of the Structured Dialogue and European strategic priorities in the field of youth, as well as to develop analytical skills to interpret, design and evaluate public policies in this field.

The structure of the programme covers five thematic blocks ranging from the history and conceptual framework of youth policies to applied tools such as social statistics and big data analysis for the evaluation of their impact. All of this is articulated through active methodologies that combine theory and practice: lectures, case studies, field work, evaluation, participatory forums...

This final report gathers the experience of implementing the module, the results obtained and the students' evaluations, with the aim of documenting the impact of the programme, identifying good practices and proposing improvements for future editions.

INTRODUCTION

Throughout its development, the programme has been implemented through a progressive structure adapted to the real context of the students, respecting at all times the contents and objectives foreseen in the original proposal. A distribution by thematic blocks throughout the programme was chosen in order to achieve a better pedagogical organisation, greater participation and a more gradual approach to learning.

Each thematic block was taught face-to-face at different times during the academic year, and not during the summer, as had initially been considered as a possible option. This decision was taken in response to the characteristics of the local context, as Salamanca is a university city which, in the summer months, sees its young population significantly reduced, largely made up of students from other regions.

Opting for a temporal distribution over the academic year has ensured a more sustained and representative participation of the programme's target audience, composed mainly of young people interested in European public policies. This modality has also favoured a better organisation of the contents and has led to a better assimilation of learning over time.

In total, 295 students participated in the classroom mode, distributed in three editions: Course 1 (94 participants), Course 2 (110 participants), and Course 3 (91 participants).

In addition, a digital version of the programme was developed through Google Classroom, an interactive platform that allows flexible access to materials, assessments and discussion forums, instead of the originally planned Moodle environment. This modification was made in order to ensure more open access.

Through a theoretical-practical approach, participants can acquire knowledge applicable to the research and design of youth-oriented public policies.

OBJECTIVES OF THE ACADEMIC PROGRAMME

General objectives

The Academic Programme in European Youth Policies and Youth Goals had the general objective of contributing to the strengthening of young people's knowledge and competences in relation to European public youth policies, in line with the principles promoted by the Jean Monnet programme. It sought to offer a comprehensive training combining conceptual analysis, case studies and the development of critical and analytical skills.

Among the main objectives of the programme are:

- To promote knowledge and critical understanding of European youth policies and the process of building the Youth Goals.
- Promote the active participation and citizenship awareness of young people in relation to public decisions that affect them.
- Training in applied methodological tools, both statistical and big data, for the analysis of youth policies and the evaluation of their impact.
- To promote research, argumentation and communication skills in the field of public youth policies.
- To create spaces for structured dialogue and critical reflection, strengthening the independent thinking and civic engagement of participants.
- Connect the Youth Goals with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and other relevant international frameworks, fostering a global and comparative vision.
- Identify effective strategies for the implementation of youth policies in different contexts.

Specific objectives per thematic block

Block 1: History and Types of European Youth Policies

- Understand the essence of youth-oriented public policies.
- Designing, implementing and evaluating European youth policies.
- Involve various actors in the formulation and implementation of such policies.
- Analyse and compare strengths and areas for improvement of youth policies in Europe, North America and Latin America.

Block 2: General Context of the Youth Goals

- Identify and explain the 11 goals of the *Youth Goals*.
- Apply the *Youth Goals* in daily practice and at different levels of action.

- Integrate the *Youth Goals* into the design, implementation and evaluation of European youth policies.
- Recognise and relate the 17 SDGs to the *Youth Goals*, assessing their reciprocal influence.

Block 3: Youth Goals as a European Youth Policy Outcome

- To get to know the Structured Dialogue, the Erasmus+ programme and the EU Youth Conferences.
- Linking the EU, European Youth Policies and the Youth Goals.
- Implement European youth policies under the Youth Goals framework (at local, regional and national level).
- Adapt the implementation of the Youth Goals in other regions, especially in North and Latin America.

Block 4: Statistical Techniques for Youth Policy Research and Youth Goals

- Understand the definitions and scope of statistical analysis and *Big Data*.
- Apply statistical analysis and *Big Data* guidelines and strategies in youth policy contexts.
- Design evaluations of European Youth Policies and *Youth Goals* using *Big Data* methods and statistical analysis.
- Comparing youth policies (European and international) using *Big Data* techniques and statistical analysis.
- Use data visualisation tools to present results and produce articles on European Youth Policies and the *Youth Goals*.

Block 5: Big Data Techniques for Youth Policy Implementation and Youth Goals

- Understand the fundamentals of statistical analysis and *Big Data* in the study of youth policies.
- Apply guidelines and strategies to implement statistical and *Big Data* methods in the research of European Youth Policies and *Youth Goals*.
- Design evaluations and comparative studies based on massive data and advanced analytical techniques, both at European and international level.
- Interpret the results to compare different youth policies through statistical analysis and *Big Data*.
- Use data visualisation tools to present and disseminate findings in articles and papers on European Youth Policies and the *Youth Goals*.

AGENDA

The programme of the academic programme versions was:

Presentation of the Jean Monnet project and the objectives of the course
Presentation of the research team and young collaborating staff
Explanation of the work dynamics and the didactic materials created.
Application of the pre-assessment survey to measure initial knowledge
Lecture on the corresponding thematic block and individual work.
Launch of key questions for discussion and participatory forum
Guided discussion among the participants.
Application of the post-assessment survey to measure acquired knowledge
Space for questions, clarifications and free participation throughout the session.
Conclusions and closure

EVENTS

General organisation of face-to-face courses

The face-to-face courses of the Academic Programme on European Youth Policies and Youth Goals followed a common structure, designed to ensure active participation, progressive learning and the integration of diverse perspectives. Each session combined an introductory phase, a central expository part and a block of interaction with the audience, maintaining a dynamic and participatory format.

The sessions began with a presentation of the Jean Monnet module and the objectives of the meeting by the teaching team and the young collaborating staff who took part in the project. The didactic materials developed to support the development of the contents were also introduced.

Before each lecture, an initial assessment survey was conducted to gauge the students' prior knowledge. After the lecture, key questions were posed as a starting point for participatory forums and guided discussions. Finally, a post-assessment survey was applied to evaluate the acquisition of knowledge, and an open space was provided for questions and dialogue with the audience.

Throughout the event, the active participation of the audience was encouraged, as well as critical reflection on the topics addressed.

Presentation sessions and participating teachers

Block 1. History and Types of European Youth Policies

Professor in charge: Dr. Pablo Biderbost

The first training block of the course, led by Dr. Pablo Biderbost, dealt with the fundamental concepts of public policy as applied to the youth field and offered a historical overview of the evolution of European policies in this field.

In the first part, students worked on various academic definitions of public policy - from decisional to constructivist approaches - which enabled them to familiarise themselves with the basic theoretical frameworks. This reflection was complemented by the analysis of the European Union's normative framework, paying special attention to the distinction between primary and secondary legislation, as well as to Article 165 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU, which is key in the formulation of education and youth policies. Subsequently, the historical evolution of European youth policies was explored through five key stages, from the 1970s to the current Strategy 2019-2027. The main institutional milestones, the approaches adopted in each phase and the increasing role given to youth as a political actor within the European integration process were discussed.

Block 2. General context of the Youth Goals

Professor in charge: Dr. Pablo Biderbost

In this second training block, Dr. Pablo Biderbost delved into the origin, structure and function of the Youth Goals as the main references for political action aimed at youth in the European context. The participatory process that led to these eleven goals, born out of the Structured Dialogue between youth and the European institutions, was presented in a clear and accessible way. The presentation allowed students to understand the principles underpinning the Youth Goals: inclusion, sustainability, active participation, equal opportunities and social cohesion. The links between the Youth Goals and the Youth Strategy 2019-2027 were also analysed, as well as their alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), highlighting their role as a connecting point between the local, the European and the global.

Students reflected on the practical relevance of each of the eleven goals, their applicability in different contexts and their transformative potential in areas such as education, civic participation, employment or the environment. In addition, concrete examples of implementation in different countries were presented, allowing for a comparative and critical analysis of their degree of fulfilment.

This block thus provided a comprehensive overview of the political and strategic context of the Youth Goals, reinforcing the idea that they are not just a declaration of intentions, but a real tool to promote more inclusive, fair and demand-driven policies for Europe's youth.

Block 3. Youth Goals as an Outcome of European Youth Policies

Professor in charge: Dr. Pablo Biderbost

In this block, Dr. Pablo Biderbost addressed the relationship between the Youth Goals and the European public policies that originate them, focusing especially on evaluation processes as a key tool to measure their impact. The public policy cycle was presented and various impact evaluation models were introduced (experimental designs, before-after, statistical match techniques, among others), explained through examples applied to the youth context. Methodological quality criteria and their connection with the European Commission's "Better Regulation" approach were also analysed. The block allowed students to understand how the effectiveness of the Youth Goals and their implementation can be evaluated from a technical, critical and data-driven perspective.

Block 4. - Statistical Techniques for Youth Policy Research and Youth Goals

Lecturer in charge: Dr. Ana Belén Nieto Librero

The session given by Dr. Ana Nieto aimed to introduce students to the use of social statistics as a fundamental tool for the analysis and evaluation of public youth policies. Throughout her presentation, she framed the need to approach these policies from an empirical perspective, based on data and evidence, in line with the principles of the EU Youth Strategy and the Youth Goals. Key concepts such as the difference between data and evidence, the basics of descriptive statistics and the main sources of information available at European level were addressed.

Concrete examples related to youth were discussed, highlighting how to interpret this information and transform it into useful evidence for the design of public policies. In addition, the complete process of analysis was presented: from data collection to critical interpretation, highlighting the importance of an ethical, comparative and contextualised reading.

Block 5. Big Data Techniques for Youth Policy Implementation and Youth Goals

Lecturer in charge: Dr. Nerea González García

The fifth and final block of the course was dedicated to exploring the role of Big Data as a tool for the analysis, design and evaluation of public policies aimed at youth. Dr. Nerea González introduced students to the fundamentals of Big Data and how its application can generate useful evidence to improve decision-making in the field of Youth Goals.

The session explained key concepts such as the difference between structured and unstructured data, the exponential growth of available data, and the need for analytical approaches adapted to complex and dynamic contexts. Multivariate techniques applied to large volumes of data were also discussed, highlighting the usefulness of dimension reduction models, clustering algorithms or interactive visual representations. The presentation included practical examples of how Big Data can reveal patterns of exclusion, inequality or participation in young people through text analysis, data mining or cross-sourcing. The importance of data visualisation as not only a technical but also a strategic tool to communicate results and generate political and social impact was underlined.

Finally, some ethical and methodological challenges associated with the use of Big Data in public policy contexts were raised, highlighting the need for responsible, comparative and territorially sensitive approaches. The block concluded by reinforcing the idea that massive data analysis does not replace political judgement, but can enrich and strengthen it if it is properly integrated into evaluation and public intervention processes.

PROGRAMME EVALUATION ACADEMIC

Knowledge acquisition

The assessment of the learning achieved by the participants throughout the training programme was carried out through pre and post questionnaires regarding the different blocks. This approach allowed to identify substantive improvements in the knowledge and understanding of key concepts related to youth policy, impact assessment and the use of data for decision-making.

Block 1 and Block 2. History and Types of European Youth Policies & General Context of the Youth Goals

Knowledge acquisition focused on the recognition and understanding of the Youth Goals as the axis of European youth policies. The results obtained in this block reflect a **very positive evolution in the knowledge of the Youth Goals**. Before the intervention, 85.4% of the students did not know these goals, and only three people correctly identified their total number. After the session, a notable improvement was observed, reaching a level of 74% correctness.

Analysis of specific questions also showed notable gains. For example, identification of false statements about Youth Goals improved from 34.1% to 58.6%, and recognition of misleading or misattributed goals remained high. In addition, some misconceptions linked to the gender equality and well-being goals were reduced.

At the attitudinal level, a significant change was also detected. Although in terms of frequency European initiatives were still little known, the perception of their value and usefulness for European youth clearly improved. Overall, this block was very effective in raising awareness and critical appraisal of European youth policies and their strategic objectives.

Block 3. Youth Goals as an Outcome of European Youth Policies

The analysis of the third block also reflects a **substantial improvement in the mastery of key methodological concepts**. One of the most outstanding advances was related to the understanding of the control and experimental groups: the percentage of correct answers doubled from 46.5% to 92.8%. Similarly, understanding of their fundamental difference (the implementation of an intervention) increased by more than 37 percentage points.

Knowledge of randomised experimentation remained stable, with 49.5% recognising its rationale before and 41% after, suggesting some difficulty in formulating the question or cognitive fatigue. Despite this, the overall data reflect a clear improvement in the understanding of essential methodological concepts.

The ability to detect conceptual errors also improved, especially in questions on impact assessment and policy planning. The percentage of correct answers on inappropriate strategies increased from 43.2% to 62.7%, and the identification of variables irrelevant to planning (such as electoral popularity) was consolidated with a 66.3% correct rate after the training.

Although some difficulties persisted around the definition of "public policy", the set of results reflects that students strengthened their critical and technical thinking around research and impact assessment, one of the programme's core themes.

Block 4 and Block 5. Statistical Techniques for Youth Policy Research and Youth Goals & Big Data Techniques for Youth Policy Implementation and Youth Goals

The results of this block were particularly encouraging, reflecting a significant transformation in the level of technical knowledge and skills. At the start, less than 24% of the trainees claimed to have a good understanding of the difference between statistics and Big Data. After the training, 80% had a clear understanding.

86.6% of the participants reported having improved their knowledge about Big Data, and 72% about statistics. These figures show a remarkable internalisation of the concepts worked on, which also translates into an improvement in the perception of their usefulness: more than 90% considered that these tools are applicable and useful for the design and implementation of public policies.

The assessment of the importance of data analysis for policy evaluation also increased: the percentage who considered it "very important" rose from an initial 38.8% to almost 50%. In addition, knowledge of real examples of application soared from 18% to 70%, indicating an improvement both conceptually and in terms of its connection to professional practice.

On the technical side, progress was equally evident. Before the block, most reported limited knowledge of descriptive statistics, data visualisation or pattern analysis. By the end of the block, most were at medium or high levels of knowledge. This growth in technical skills reinforces the formative impact of the programme and its orientation towards the strategic use of data for public decision-making.

Satisfaction with the activity

Although the quantitative data from the satisfaction questionnaire applied to Course 1 were not kept, complete and consistent results are available for Courses 2 and 3, allowing us to provide a representative assessment of the overall satisfaction with the academic programme.

Overall student satisfaction with the courses was remarkably high, as reflected in the surveys collected in versions 2 and 3 of the academic programme.

In organisational terms, the vast majority of students rated both the structure of the sessions and their planning positively. In both editions, participants rated key

aspects such as the organisation, the quality of the content, the usefulness of the information and the conditions of the environment with scores mostly at the top of the scale.

In terms of organisation, the vast majority of students rated both the structure of the sessions and their planning positively. For example, the majority of students in year 3 rated this aspect as "very good" (48.3%) or "good" (38.3%), representing 86.6% positive ratings. In year 2, this rating was also among the highest (3 or 4 out of 4 on the scale used) . This highlights clarity in the development of the content, efficient time management and appropriate transitions between blocks.

With regard to the adequacy of the information received, 88.4% of students in year 3 considered that it was adequate (adding together the levels of "very good" and "good"), while in year 2, comments were highlighted which positively valued the clarity and usefulness of the material shared.

The quality of the content and presentations was one of the most highly praised aspects. More than 90% of students in course 3 rated them as "very good" or "good", and in course 2 the scores also ranged between 3 and 4, thus showing an improvement in subsequent sessions. Frequent comments such as "pleasant and concise explanation", "fluency of presentation" or "clarity of concepts" support this perception. The topics covered were considered relevant, up-to-date and closely connected to youth reality, both from a theoretical and applied approach.

Finally, the facilities also received a positive reception, especially in year 3, where 73.3% of the student body marked the option "very well" and 21.7% "well", with negative evaluations practically non-existent. The facilities used received a high degree of acceptance, especially in the last edition (Faculty of Economics and Business), where almost three out of four participants gave the highest score. The layout of the space, the accessibility and the environment were all elements that were mentioned as conducive to learning.

A summary of participants' ratings of each of the satisfaction items in courses 2 and 3 can be found in Figure 1.

Figure1 Assessment of organisational and pedagogical aspects (Course 2, left, and Course 3, right)

A breakdown of the assessment of the above-mentioned aspects for year 3 can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 22 Assessment of organisational and pedagogical aspects (Course 3)

The qualitative information collected through the open questions in the satisfaction questionnaires reflects a largely positive experience among the participants in the academic programme. The evaluations highlight the interest in the contents, the educational value of the activities and the quality of the teaching staff's presentation, while also including constructive suggestions that show a critical and committed attitude on the part of the students.

One of the aspects most highlighted as a strength was the **clarity** of the lecturers' **explanations**. Terms such as "*pleasant*", "*concise*", "*fluent*" or "*understandable*" were repeated in numerous comments, especially valuing the ability to explain complex concepts such as public policy, statistics or Big Data in an understandable and didactic way. This quality was considered key to learning and generated a climate of trust and closeness that encouraged active participation.

Another central theme was the **interest and perceived usefulness** of the content. Students expressed a receptive attitude towards topics that, in many cases, were new to them: data collection, statistical analysis or the use of evidence to design public policies. Many indicated that these contents were particularly relevant to their academic training, especially in degrees such as Sociology, Political Science or Statistics. Comments such as "*it has helped me to clarify doubts*", "*I learned a*

lot" or "now I understand better how data works" reflect a significant appropriation of

the knowledge imparted

Some participants highlighted that the experience contributed to their professional training and, in some cases, to their academic performance. A clear personal, practical and formative added value is perceived.

In addition, the **link between theoretical content and its social applicability** was positively valued, highlighting how the focus of the course made it possible to connect statistics and data analysis with real issues such as inequality, youth participation or public policy planning. This approach was recognised as a tool for citizen empowerment that invites to think critically about reality. This approach was interpreted by the students as a form of awareness-raising and critical education, helping them to understand the value of data not only at a technical level, but also from a citizen's perspective.

One of the most significant achievements of the activities has been their ability to bring the world of public policy closer to young people in an accessible, clear and motivating way. The responses reflect that, beyond acquiring theoretical knowledge, students have been able to understand the real applicability of these topics, as well as their connection to everyday life and the current European context.

In terms of **format and dynamics**, most participants described the experience as participatory and dynamic and the opportunity to learn about public policy from a new perspective. The possibility of resolving doubts in real time, the use of visual tools and the moments of interaction were appreciated. However, some people proposed to **increase the spaces for direct participation**, asking for more moments to intervene, share ideas and ask questions in an active way. This request shows an involved and open attitude to collaborative learning.

In addition, **some participants requested more in-depth content related to the 2030 Agenda**, expressing interest in better understanding the connections between the SDGs and youth policies. This interest reinforces the value of continuing to incorporate global issues into the focus of the course and future work.

On the other hand, **a specific language barrier** was also identified, as some questionnaires were only available in Spanish, making it difficult for non-Spanish speakers to fully participate. This observation highlights the need to further adapt the materials for international audiences.

Finally, in terms of **organisational aspects**, although most of the comments did not point out any problems, there were some suggestions focused on the length of the sessions. It was proposed to slightly reduce the time dedicated to the presentation in order to maintain the attention of the group, especially in blocks with a greater theoretical load.

Some responses included profound reflections on the situation of youth, the importance of feeling an active part of society, and the role that statistics and science can play in social transformation.

Overall, the qualitative evaluations point to a valuable training experience that was well received by the public, highlighting the pedagogical clarity, the relevance of the content and the possibility of applying what was learned to real contexts. The suggestions collected do not contradict this positive assessment, but rather show a committed student body that seeks to continue to deepen the contents, with more participatory, accessible and applied spaces.

CONCLUSIONS

The Academic Programme on European Youth Policies and the Youth Goals has proved to be a high impact training experience, both for the quality and relevance of its contents and for the level of involvement and learning achieved by the participants, with a high number of them. The modular and progressive structure, which articulated five thematic blocks from the fundamentals of youth policies to the use of advanced analytical tools such as statistics and Big Data, allowed for a coherent and rigorous training path.

The results obtained in the knowledge acquisition assessment reflect a significant improvement in the understanding of the Youth Goals, European policy frameworks and methodological tools for research and evaluation of public policies. In all thematic blocks, there was an increase in the levels of knowledge, accompanied by a critical and committed attitude on the part of the students.

Particularly noteworthy are the advances observed in the understanding of key methodological concepts such as control and experimental groups, the use of randomised experimentation and the identification of good practices in impact evaluation. Significant progress was also made in the appropriation of statistical tools and Big Data, not only at the conceptual level, but also in their applicability to real contexts of public policy formulation and evaluation.

The positive feedback from the students - both in the quantitative questionnaires and in the open-ended responses - reinforces this overall impression. The clarity of the lecturers' presentation, the usefulness of the content taught and the possibility of connecting what was learned with real experiences and current youth challenges were repeatedly highlighted. The programme was perceived as an innovative and transformative training opportunity, enabling young people to acquire tools to critically analyse their reality and actively participate in public decision-making processes.

The suggestions collected - such as the demand for more time for active participation or the inclusion of multilingual materials - offer valuable clues for future editions, in which the training proposal can be further refined.

As a limitation, it is difficult to carry out a continuous follow-up of the students after the face-to-face sessions. However, continuity mechanisms were established, such as the sending of certificates and open access to the materials in the digital version of the programme.

In addition, the results of the programme have led to the development of an associated MOOC, in which 80 people have already participated in its online version, thus broadening its scope and consolidating its vocation of openness, sustainability and social transfer of knowledge.

With a view to future actions, it is considered relevant to deepen the monitoring of the training impact in the medium term, incorporating tools that allow a more accurate assessment of the transfer of the knowledge acquired to academic, professional or social contexts. Furthermore, the adaptation of the training proposal to other geographical environments is identified as a potential line of interest, especially in regions such as Latin America, where Youth Goals can also offer a useful reference framework for the design of youth-oriented public policies. These possible developments, open to the collaboration of other institutions, would allow for continuity and international projection of the approach worked on in this programme.

In short, the YGRC team considers that the programme has more than fulfilled its objectives: to foster critical knowledge on European youth policies, to train in analytical methodologies, and to bring public decision-making closer to the youth world from an empirical, inclusive and participatory perspective. Its implementation lays a solid foundation for the further development of evidence-based citizenship education initiatives with a real impact on European youth.

#YGRC: Youth Goals Research Centre (101047538)

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